

THE DOMINANCE OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IN THE VICTORIAN
ERA

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Annotation: *This article describes stereotypes about women during the Victorian era, the attitudes of society and women themselves to these innovations, and the consequences and outcomes of the period.*

Keywords: *stereotype, woman, Victorian era, society, man, inhibitions, time.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье описываются стереотипы по отношению женщин в Викторианскую эпоху, отношение общества и самих женщин к данным нововведения, а также последствия и результаты данного периода.*

Ключевые слова: *стереотип, женщина, Викторианская эпоха, общество, мужчина, запреты, время.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Viktoriya davridagi ayollarning stereotiplari, jamiyat va ayollarning o'zlarining ushbu yangiliklarga munosabati, shuningdek, ushbu davrning oqibatlari va natijalari tasvirlangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *stereotip, ayol, Viktoriya davri, jamiyat, erkak, taqiqlar, vaqt.*

Since antiquity, people have lived by patterns and traditions. A prime example of this is England in the mid-19th century, where tradition played a big role in society.

Queen Victoria ascended to the throne, an attribute of the Golden Age period. At this time, Britain was a powerful country with a rich culture. It had a stable government, a growing state and expanding influence. It was during this time that the British Empire became a major industrial and innovative colonial power, the consequence of which was a marked change in all aspects of life: economic, socio-political, value-based.

Britain as a global political power was supported by a strong economy that grew rapidly during the Victorian era. Britain became the richest country in Europe. Many Britons still consider this era to be the best in England's history, while it left only deep scars on other countries. But more than political and economic successes, Britons are proud of the moral qualities in society that were instilled by the Queen towards the people of the whole country.

The ideals of marriage and family have long defined gender relations in English culture. The moral requirements of the Victorians were very strict and were based on a number of prohibitions, among them "prohibitions against doing things", prohibitions against "modelling actions through the languages of culture", and there were strict "means of enforcing" these prohibitions [5].

Balls, lavish living and dressing up, gallant cavaliers. It would have been everything any girl of that era could have wanted. But what was it really like to live in a society which considered women to be unequal creatures to men and sometimes even slaves? In a society where the organs of a woman, making her different from men, were identified with pathology. In a society where Victorian stereotypes about gender and double standards took over [1].

In the 21st century, it is extremely difficult for Westerners to imagine women's lack of rights in the Victorian era. A shift in gender roles was noticed at the time. Their definitions were expressed more clearly than at any other time in history. Before that time, women were allowed to work equally with their husbands and families. Family businesses such as the shop under the house helped women not only to earn money, but also to have time to run their households. But developments in the 19th century led to a dramatic change in the family structure. Men began to travel more and more to work, while their wives, daughters and sisters increasingly stayed at home for the day. Their duties consisted only of running and overseeing the quality of household chores done by servants.

Both sexes now lived in a "doctrine of separate spheres", crossing paths only over food. The ideology of this separation was based on the division of natural characteristics defining into 'men' and 'women'. This meant only that the two sexes were completely different in nature, and therefore destined for completely different things.

'The man's power is active, progressive, defensive. He is eminently the doer, the creator, the discoverer, the defender. His intellect is for speculation, and invention; his energy for adventure war, and for conquest... but the woman's power is for rule, not for battle - and her intellect is not for invention or creation, but for sweet ordering, arrangement, and decision... she must be enduringly, incorruptibly good; instinctively, infallibly wise, wise not for self-development, but for self-renunciation: wise, not that she may set herself above her husband, but that she man never fail from his side.' [3].

In this quote, the critic and sociologist shows people the division of men and women in the society of the time. The emergence of strict gender ideals and stereotypes resulted in men having more power over members of the female sex who were completely disadvantaged in their rights. Men stood higher on the evolutionary ladder according to Darwin's theory of "Survival of the fittest". This a priori considered women to be weak and incapable of doing anything.

A lady of the Victorian era is a delicate creature, not independent, in need of constant guardianship and support from the stronger sex, and from the perspective of all men of the time - slightly mentally handicapped.

As an example, an amusing phrase describing the realities of society in relation to women at that time is given:

When addressing the ladies, by no means underestimate the intellectual level of the conversation. Compliment them by convincing them that you consider them capable of understanding the conversation on a par with men [2].

Men considered women to be emotionally unstable and therefore had no decision-making power whatsoever. Marriage for a woman of that time was characterized by the

end of her existence, because after marriage she became one with her husband, who took control of the lady's leadership, degrading her to the level of a slave. The husband took control not only over all the wife's property but also over her body. It was acceptable in the eyes of the law to beat and even rape his wife without fear of punishment.

Victorian men believed they were driven by their intelligence and intellect, feeling a purpose in dominating and controlling women, while women were seen as something irrational, submissive, waiting to be implanted in an environment created by men. Worthy in their terms, women were identified with the 'domestic angel' or the ivy supporting the mighty oak tree. Wives became nothing more than a symbol of their husbands. And most ladies were quite happy with this state of affairs. After all, uncomfortable dresses were not the most important problem at the time. All the more so that living in affluence, not knowing hunger, and suffering only from boredom, they were no more miserable than women of any other era.

But rebellious souls have always been born.

However, it was not ideas of civil rights and freedom, but a more down-to-earth problem, which became the idea of the struggle for equal rights. Most working class families could not afford to implement this doctrine of separation because they could not survive and feed their family on their husband's salary alone. In order to earn more money for their family, women went to work. But because of the stereotype that women were too weak to work full-time jobs, there were fewer and fewer jobs for women and the type of work was very limited. It was also common for women to be paid much less than men, even if they did equal work. It was not a good prospect to work in a house, especially with children on her own. Under these conditions, a woman condemned herself and her children to hard, sometimes even slave labour. The only alternative to earning a living for a Victorian woman was to sell her body, that is, prostitution. The poor economic situation forced women, despite their aversion to the process, to step over themselves and start selling their bodies. However, prostitution was one of the ways for Victorian women to become economically independent. It is true that the consequences of the widespread prostitution in England led to an increased number of venereal diseases. The government's decision to force the treatment of "fallen" ladies caused a public outcry, and led to women rallying against the abuse [6].

Also, the first organising movement was the 'Temperance movement', pushing for restrictions on the sale of alcohol, and a ban on the sale to minors. However, ignored, as the stereotype of women at the time suggested that they did not have the right to vote, women were forced to fight for their rights to vote and to be part of the government. Thus, over time, all the waves of women's discontent and protests developed into the first wave of feminism, which is still simmering in society today. Although this movement was not successful in changing women, we should not forget that the unjustified stereotypes created by Queen Victoria about women have long existed in modern society to this day.

In the middle of the 19th - century crime and poverty were an inseparably mixed matter and most of the youngsters who suffered prison sentences were the preys of poverty; unwanted by their family, church and state. During the Industrial Revolution period, a mass of humanity flowed from the countryside into cities and towns, especially

London, without any promise of stable homes or shelters. Children ran wild on the streets, fighting for life as best as they could, oftentimes by crime and only the tough and quickwitted held out. They had no education and did pretty much whatever they wanted. They never heard words of kindness, only the language of the people they met in the streets which they copied: various curses, shouting and vulgar language. Young children, who were running in the streets to fend for themselves, were never taught or told what was right and what was wrong; for instance, they taking food from the market tables without paying for it was wrong and they were going to be punished for it if they were caught. It was more of a game to them which they played daily (Duckworth 11). Jennie Duckworth, in her book *Fagin's Children: Criminal Children in Victorian England* quotes Charles Dickens, who in the preface to the 1841 edition of *Oliver Twist* drew an outline to which many homeless children were connected: "The cold, wet, shelter's midnight streets of London; the foul and frowsy dens, where vice is closely packed and lacks the room to turn; the haunts of hunger and disease, the shabby rags that scarcely hold together: where are the attractions of these things"? (Duckworth 2). Life for the street youngsters was troublesome and cruel. The authorities regarded them as being only a social inconvenience. If there was enough proper work available, most of them would have been inclined to work, but most turned to stealing. Because many of them did not have any family or home to return to, they looked for lodging houses as a shelter (if the day's stealing had been successful); but if otherwise, they stayed under bridges, or simply slept on the pavement. They were often wet, freezing, hungry and dirty. The behaviour of these children received public disapproval [4, 2-3].

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